

Pianist Motion Capture with the Kinect Depth Camera

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ABSTRACT

Sensing pianist movements is useful for various applications fields such as electronic music, music performance research, musician medicine, and piano pedagogy. This paper contributes an unobtrusive, markerless method to capture pianist movements based on depth sensing. The method was realized using the Kinect depth camera and evaluated in comparison with 2D marker tracking.

1. INTRODUCTION

Movements are an integral part of musical performance. They are not only necessary to operate the instrument but are also perceived by the audience and can influence the musical experience.

Capturing musicians' movements enables new interactive performance systems: The movements can be used for controlling live electronics [1], for synchronizing computer playback to a human performance [2], and for instrument pedagogy [5]. A further use case is empirical research. Early examples of such movement-based research are the experiments by Ortmann [6] and Hodgson [7], which date back to the 30ies of the last century. Today, research on musicians' movements continues to be an active field.

This paper contributes an unobtrusive, markerless method to capture pianist movement from depth imaging. To get a better understanding of potential application fields for the method, it is informative to identify existing uses of pianist movement sensing in the literature:

- **Electronic music:** Pianist movements can be used to control synthesized and electromechanically generated sound. Inertial sensing & electromyography [8] as well as continuous key position measurement [9] have been used as input modalities.
- **Feedback systems for instrument pedagogy:** Pedagogical feedback systems can provide knowledge of performance (KP) feedback on the student's playing movements [10, 11].
- **Music performance research:** Here the movements are analyzed to examine performance phe-

nomena, e. g., different types of touch were shown to correlate with timing accuracy [12].

- **Musician medicine:** Here the movement data is often used to examine causes of music-related injuries, e. g., the forces that act on the musculoskeletal system during piano performance have been examined [13].

Overview: First, existing methods for capturing pianist movements and algorithms and frameworks for Kinect-based motion capture are discussed (Section 2). Then, the hardware setup (Section 3) and the depth image analysis method (Section 4) are presented. The evaluation of the method (Section 5) provides a comparison with 2D marker tracking and shows that the method is real-time capable. Conclusions are discussed in Section 6.

2. RELATED WORK

This section discusses existing methods for capturing pianist movements (Section 2.1) and algorithms for performing motion capture with the Kinect (Section 2.2).

2.1 Pianist Motion Capture

Ideally, movement sensing would be highly accurate, cheap, unobtrusive (no devices, cables or markers need to be worn), be robust to lighting conditions etc., require minimal setup & calibration effort, and no post processing. In the literature, pianist movements have been sensed using motion capture systems, image processing, and inertial systems. These approaches, which will be discussed in the following, have individual advantages in comparison to our method.

2.1.1 Optical motion capture

Optical motion capture systems track movements in three dimensions based on markers placed on the body. The markers are detected on multiple cameras so that the 3D position can be triangulated [14]. Optical motion capture has been used in various studies in music performance research [12, 15] and musician medicine [16, 17]. In comparison with optical motion capture, the main advantages and disadvantages of our method are:

- **Cost:** Movement tracking based on the Kinect is much more affordable.
- **Post-Processing:** Optical motion capture systems require time-intensive post-processing due to lost and confused markers.

- Unobtrusiveness: When using optical motion capture, markers have to be placed on the player’s body, which is not necessary in our approach.
- Accuracy: Optical motion capture systems are much more accurate. VICON motion capture systems are claimed to have sub-millimeter accuracy while the depth resolution of the Kinect is in the centimeter range [18].

2.1.2 Image Processing

Another option is optical tracking based on a single RGB-camera using image processing techniques. Gorodnichy & Yogeswaran developed a system for hand tracking [19]. Their system is limited to tracking hand position. It does not provide the position of other points of interest such as the wrist, the elbow, etc. Image processing based on RGB-cameras has been used for studies in music performance research [20] and musician medicine [13]. Here active and passive marker based approaches were used. In comparison with RGB-camera-based tracking, the main advantages and disadvantages of our method are:

- Robustness: Camera-Based movement tracking is vulnerable to lighting conditions, which is not an issue with the Kinect depth camera.
- Three dimensions: With the Kinect it is possible to determine 3D position.

2.1.3 Inertial sensing

Inertial sensing has been used for movement based piano pedagogy [10, 11] and augmented piano systems [8]. The main advantages and disadvantages of our method in comparison with inertial sensing are:

- Unobtrusiveness: Using the Kinect, no devices have to be worn on the player’s body.
- Absolute position: Inertial sensors can only provide orientation values and not the absolute position.
- Accuracy: Inertial sensing is able to record very fine movements while the Kinect has depth sensing accuracy limitations in the centimeter range [18].

2.2 Motion Capture with the Kinect

The standard algorithm used for determining joint positions in the Kinect is based on a decision forest that is trained based on a very large synthetic data set. This data set is constructed from motion capture data. The classification of body parts is performed per pixel. Based on the body part labeling performed by the decision forest, the joints are determined [18].

The decision forest was trained for conditions (free body movement, standing posture) very different from the conditions we face (sitting posture, hands close to the keys). Therefore, the joint detection solution shipped with the Kinect does not function properly in our scenario. While the general approach described in [18] could be applied to our problem, creating sufficient training data would be

Figure 1. Hardware setup: The Kinect is mounted above the keyboard.

very time-intensive. Therefore, we adopted an appearance-based approach to detect body landmarks in the depth image.

There are frameworks for tangible interaction such as dSensingNI [21] that provide interaction support and touch detection on ordinary objects based on Kinect depth sensing. However, these frameworks are not usable for full-body motion capture as they are usually limited to tracking the hand (and the objects) only.

3. KINECT CHARACTERISTICS AND HARDWARE SETUP

Before delving into the algorithmic details (see the next section), some properties of the Kinect and the hardware setup are discussed briefly in order to provide a good understanding of the starting position.

The Kinect has two cameras: one provides RGB-images and the other one is used for depth sensing. Depth sensing is realized using structured infrared light. Both cameras provide images with a resolution of 640 x 480 at a rate of 30 FPS. Furthermore, the Kinect has an integrated accelerometer sensor, which can be used to determine its inclination [22].

Figure 1 shows the hardware setup. The Kinect is mounted over the keyboard 2–2.5 m over the ground so that the Kinect cameras view the entire keyboard range. The Kinect is aligned in a way so that the view on the keyboard is as can be seen in Figure 2. For the analysis, our method has to know the position of the keyboard area. Currently, the user defines the area using a GUI but we plan to perform this step automatically using color-based detection from the RGB image as described in [19].

Figure 2. View from the Kinect: depth image (left) and RGB image (right)

Figure 3. Analysis results: the recognized positions are marked with a red squares.

4. DEPTH IMAGE ANALYSIS

In the following the depth image analysis method is described. It is composed of the steps

- Head detection
- Shoulder detection
- Arm silhouette detection
- Wrist detection
- Elbow detection
- Hand activity detection
- Hand detection.

The result of the depth image analysis are 3D coordinates of landmarks on the player's body, in particular: the center of the head, the shoulders, the wrist, and the hand (see Figure 3). The positions are initially calculated as 3D coordinates in relation to the Kinect coordinate system. Using linear transformation, the coordinates are transformed into an easier-to-interpret coordinate system.

4.1 Conventions

Let $d(x, y)$ be the depth value provided by the Kinect camera for the pixel (x, y) . Since the camera views the keyboard are from above a small value of $d(x, y)$ denotes a position high over the ground. Instead of $d(x, y)$, we will often use the term “height of the pixel”, which we define as

$$h(x, y) = -d(x, y)$$

so that higher values of $h(x, y)$ represent a higher “height”. This definition simplifies the explanations in the following sections. Note however that there is a slight difference between this definition and the actual height over ground since the orientation of the Kinect is not completely vertical but sloped.

4.2 Head Detection

The head is detected based on being the highest area in the image. For this purpose, thresholding is applied to the depth image; a pixel (x, y) is detected as a head pixel if the height exceeds a threshold t , i. e., if $h(x, y) > t$. The threshold is adapted on a frame-by-frame basis so that the head can be robustly tracked despite of 3D head movements and different body heights of users. For this purpose the bounding box of the head pixels is determined to compute the surface area (width · length). Since the Kinect is placed in a fixed location over the keyboard, the range for reasonable values of the head surface area is known in advance. If the computed surface area differs from the expected surface area, the threshold t is modified by a small amount. Since the Kinect provides depth samples at a rate of 30 FPS, the threshold t converges quickly. The head center is detected as the mean of the head pixels.

In order to increase the efficiency, the head detection is confined to region of interest centered around the head area detected in the previous step.

4.3 Shoulder Detection

To detect the shoulders, the image regions to the left and the right of the head are examined. For this purpose, one pixel wide vertical image slices are examined one by one to determine the highest point on each vertical slice. The search area is confined to an area close to the head where the shoulder may be expected to be located. The x - and y -coordinates of each of the highest points are stored only after the corresponding height $h(x, y)$ has been examined in order to separate between shoulder and background pixels (floor, chair, etc.). This is done by thresholding. The shoulder position is then determined by calculating the median x - and y -values of the stored points.

4.4 Arm Silhouette Detection

Arm silhouette detection finds the outer boundary for the entire arm and the inner boundary of the forearm (see Figure 4). The outer and the inner boundaries are detected with a localized edge detection algorithm.

The algorithm for outer boundary detection examines horizontal slices of the image by examining pixels one-by-one moving outward, away from the body center. A boundary is detected if there is a large drop in reported height (background pixels such as floor and chair pixels are considerably lower in height).

For the detection of the inner boundary, a set of “candidate pixels” are determined as a series of two steps:

- Search of the starting position (step 1): Beginning from the outer boundary coordinates, the pixels are examined one-by-one moving horizontally towards

Figure 4. Arm silhouette detection results: inner boundary (aqua) and outer boundary (green).

the center of the body until a boundary, i. e., a considerable drop in measured height, is detected.

- Local search (step 2): Given a valid detection of the inner boundary in the previous line, a local search horizontally in the current line is performed to find the boundary. If the local search fails, a new starting position is searched (step 1).

The largest locally continuous run of candidate pixels is then determined. This is the inner boundary. The result of the arm silhouette detection is shown in Figure 4.

4.5 Wrist Detection

The wrist is detected based on its appearance. The shape of the arm and the hand narrows in the direction from the arm towards the wrist and markedly widens after the wrist when the hand begins.

To detect the wrist, the following algorithm is employed: First, the minimal arm diameter is determined. For this purpose, the closest outer boundary pixel (Euclidian distance) is determined for each inner boundary pixel. A threshold is calculated by adding a constant to the minimal arm diameter. The wrist is recognized as the first (in an ordering from top, i. e., away from the keyboard, to bottom, i. e., close to the keyboard) inner / outer boundary pixel pair where the arm diameter exceeds the threshold. The reported wrist position is the the point just halfway between the inner and the outer boundary pixel.

4.6 Elbow Detection

The elbow, or to be more precise the crook of the arm (an-
te-cubital fossa), is detected based on

- The shoulder position (see Section 4.3)
- The outer boundary of the arm (see Section 4.4)
- The wrist position (see Section 4.5).

The elbow is detected based on its distance from the shoulder and the wrist. In order to determine the position of the elbow, we need to be able to measure the distance along the arm. For this purpose a virtual track along the arm, marked by a set of points, is created (see Figure 5). The

Figure 5. The virtual tracks

virtual track's pathway is similar to the outer boundary. It differs in two ways:

1. Due to wrinkles in the clothing, the outer boundary is rather irregular so that the true direction of the arm is not well reflected. Therefore, a discretization is performed. The effect of this operation is basically a sub-sampling operations, which reduces the influence of the high-frequency wrinkle artifacts.
2. The virtual track should run through the center of the arm. In order to assert this, it is required that the virtual track runs through three support points. It starts at the shoulder (support point 1) and ends at the wrist (support point 3). Furthermore, it has also to run through the center of the arm at the position where the first inner boundary pixel of the forearm is detected. This position is calculated by finding the nearest outer boundary pixel of that inner boundary pixel and calculating the point just half-way in-between them (support point 2). Linear interpolation is used to make the virtual track run through the shoulder (support point 1) and support point 2. From support point 2 to the wrist (support point 3), the location of the virtual track is determined as the center position between the corresponding inner and outer boundary pixels.

The virtual track spans a three-dimensional path through space. Along this path, the length of the arm from shoulder to wrist is calculated. The elbow is detected based on the ratio between the length of the upper and lower arm. This parameter is taken from an anatomical study [23] but can also be redefined by the user if necessary.

4.7 Hand Activity Detection

Because hand, fingers, and piano keys are very close most of the time, separation between body pixels and background pixels (i. e., keyboard pixels), based on the depth imaging is challenging. In order to perform the segmentation, background subtraction is used. A pixel in the background image is updated if the newly reported height of that pixel is lower then the old value. When the hand hovers over a key, the height reading of that region is higher

and therefore no update of the pixel in the background image will take place. Over time, the background image will converge to the true three-dimensional structure of the keyboard. Hand activity is detected with thresholding after background subtraction.

Due to noise in the depth measurement of the Kinect, the height of keyboard pixels is occasionally underestimated. This would lead to a permanently wrong background image and would continuously produce false positive hand activity detections. False positive hand activity detections are usually small localized blobs. It is therefore possible to filter them out using morphological operations (first erode, then dilate). Since false positive detections result from incorrect background pixels, the height of the corresponding background pixels is increased by a constant amount. In that way background image errors do not accumulate over time.

4.8 Hand Detection

For the detection of hand position, an image is synthesized: It contains, the arm shape from the wrist onward, given by the inner and outer boundary as determined before (see Section 4.4), which is filled and combined with the hand activity image (see Section 4.7). The resulting image is filtered with morphological operators (erode and dilute) in order to diminish the influence of the individual finger outlines so that only the outline of the back of the hand remains visible. The center of the resulting shape is then recognized as the hand position.

4.9 Linear Transformation

Up to now, the results, i.e., the head, shoulder, elbow, wrist, and hand positions, are reported in 3D coordinates relative to the Kinect depth camera. This coordinate system, however, is not intuitive for our applications. E.g., the origin (0, 0, 0) of the coordinate system is the position of the Kinect itself. Therefore, the results are transformed to a coordinate system centered around the keyboard (see Figure 6).

Figure 6. The analysis results are transformed into an easier-to-interpret coordinate system: The origin of the coordinate system is located on the frontmost part (towards the player) of the center key of an 88-key piano (d'). The x-axis runs horizontally along the keys to the right. The y-axis runs horizontally into the piano. The z-axis runs vertically upwards.

Figure 7. LED lights were used to mark the body landmarks

The alignment of the x- and y-axes of the Kinect is known in advance due to the fixed hardware setup (see Section 3). The slope of the Kinect is determined based on the internal accelerometer. The position of the center key can be deduced from the keyboard area known to our application (see Section 3) and its height difference to the Kinect can be determined from depth sensing. Using this information, the corresponding linear transformation is then calculated. After this transformation the results are available in the keyboard-based coordinate system.

4.10 Implementation Details

Our method was implemented using OpenCV 2.0 for image processing, OpenNI for acquiring the depth and the RGB images, and the Freenect framework for reading the accelerometer data.

5. EVALUATION

This evaluation addresses two questions:

- How accurate is the body landmark recognition from depth images?
- Is the analysis real-time capable?

The first question is answered by comparing the results of the analysis method to a simple but very accurate 2D tracking method using active markers. The second question is answered by time measurements.

5.1 Marker Tracking

We used small (custom-built) LED lights (see Figure 7) to mark the body landmarks to be tracked. We used green-colored LEDs instead of infrared light in order to avoid impeding the infrared light based depth sensing capability of the Kinect. The LED lights were attached to the body using elastic bands (wrist / crook of the arm), sewing the lights to clothing (head / shoulders), and double-sided adhesive strips (hand).

The marker identification was done using the RGB-images provided by the Kinect. For this purpose thresholding was applied to the green channel of the image, followed by a contour finding algorithm. The marker position was recognized as the center of each contour, which provides a very well localized marker identification. Each marker was labeled as head marker, shoulder marker, etc. based on its position in the image and its geometrical relation to the other markers.

5.2 Accuracy of Body Landmark Identification

In order to determine the accuracy of the body landmark identification, the positions estimated by the depth image analysis were compared to the measured marker positions. Relying on the factory calibration of the depth and the RGB cameras, the Euclidian distance between the points estimated from the depth image and measured by marker identification were computed.

The mean distance and the root mean square of the distance were used as evaluation metrics. Let $p(i)$ be the value reported by the depth image analysis and $q(i)$ be the value reported by marker tracking for frame i . Then the mean distance is computed as

$$mean = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \|p(i) - q(i)\|$$

and the root mean square of the distance as

$$RMS = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \|p(i) - q(i)\|^2}.$$

The results of the accuracy metrics are shown in Table 1. To provide a better understanding of the results, Table 1 provides not only the pixel values but also an upper boundary of the deviation in cm.

Point	mean	RMS
Head	11.9 pixel (2.8 cm)	13.3 pixel (3.1 cm)
Shoulder	18.4 pixel (4.3 cm)	19.4 pixel (4.5 cm)
Elbow	20.6 pixel (4.8 cm)	21.0 pixel (4.9 cm)
Wrist	19.0 pixel (4.4 cm)	19.5 pixel (4.5 cm)
Hand	11.8 pixel (2.7 cm)	13.6 pixel (3.2 cm)

Table 1. Accuracy of the body landmark identification. The reported unit is pixel distance. The equivalent deviation in cm (upper boundary) is provided in parentheses. The conversion from pixels to cm makes the simplifying assumption that the points are located in the height of the keyboard. For all points that lie above the keyboard height, especially head and shoulder points the true error in cm is actually smaller.

We evaluated the system based on a performance of Chopin’s Etude op. 10 No. 1. The performance of this virtuosic piece requires large and quick movements over the entire keyboard range, which makes the piece well-suited for the evaluation. The first bars of the piece are shown in Figure 8. While the left hand operates in a rather confined area, the right hand continuously moves up and down the keyboard. This movement is visible in the graph contained in Figure 8, which also compares the Kinect-based to the marker-based tracking.

5.3 Real-Time Capability

In order to be usable for augmented piano and piano pedagogy applications, the analysis of the depth image has to

be performed in real-time. To assure this, the described method has been implemented using common optimization techniques such as regions of interest (see Section 4.2 and 4.7) to minimize computational complexity and efficient algorithms such as using quicksort when computing median values (see Section 4.3).

The run time of the depth image analysis was evaluated using timers. Both individual run time per analysis step as well as the total run time to analyze a single depth frame were determined (see Table 2). The entire analysis takes 10.2 ms per frame (on a 2.53 GHz Intel Core 2 Duo computer with 4GB RAM) so that minimal latency and real-time capability can be provided on current computer hardware.

Analysis step	Time
Head	1.5 ms
Shoulder	0.9 ms
Arm silhouette	1.2 ms
Wrist	0.1 ms
Elbow	0.01 ms
Hand activity	1.7 ms
Hand detection	4.8 ms
Total	10.2 ms

Table 2. Time to analyze a single depth frame for each analysis step and in total.

6. CONCLUSION

This paper contributed a method to capture pianist movements from depth imaging. The main advantages of our approach in comparison to existing options are its low cost when based on the Kinect and its unobtrusiveness (no devices, cables or markers have to be placed on the body). Our evaluation shows that our method is able to detect the relevant body landmarks with good accuracy and in real-time. Obviously, the limits of the Kinect in depth resolution make our solution compare unfavorably with state-of-the-art multi-camera optical motion capture systems, which are currently the gold standard for highly accurate motion capturing. However, future advances in depth sensing technology may alleviate this shortcoming to some extent. Currently, the main application areas for our method are augmented piano-based instruments and piano pedagogy systems as these application areas are particularly cost-sensitive and require less accuracy than rigorous scientific examination in the areas of musician medicine and music performance research.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] J. Paradiso and N. Gershenfeld, “Musical applications of electric field sensing,” *Computer music journal*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 69–89, 1997.
- [2] N. Rasamimanana, F. Guedy, N. Schnell, J.-P. Lambert, and F. Bevilacqua, “Three pedagogical scenarios using

Figure 8. The first bars of Chopin’s Etude op. 10 No. 1 (top). The pitches rise for the duration of one bar and then fall for the same duration. To play this musical pattern, the player moves the right arm horizontally along the keyboard. This is also visible in the graphs (bottom), which depict the tracking results with the Kinect (red) and the marker-based method (blue).

the sound and gesture lab,” in *4th i-Maestro Workshop on Technology-Enhanced Music Education*, 2008.

[3] R. Dannenberg, “An on-line algorithm for real-time accompaniment,” in *International Computer Music Conference 1984*, 1984.

[4] B. Vercoe, “The synthetic performer in the context of live performance,” in *International Computer Music Conference 1984*, 1984.

[5] T. Großhauser, U. Großekathöfer, and T. Hermann, “New sensors and pattern recognition techniques for string instruments,” in *New Interfaces for Musical Expression 2010*, 2010.

[6] O. Ortmann, *The Physiological Mechanics of Piano Technique*. K. Paul, Trench, Trubner & Co., 1929.

[7] P. Hodgson, *Motion study and violin bowing*. London: L.H. Lavender & Co, 1934.

[8] S. Nicolls, “Twenty-first century piano,” in *New Interfaces for Musical Expression 2009*, 2009, pp. 203–206.

[9] A. McPherson and Y. Kim, “Augmenting the acoustic piano with electromagnetic string actuation and continuous key position sensing,” in *New Interfaces for Musical Expression 2010*, 2010.

[10] A. Hadjakos, “Sensor-based feedback for piano pedagogy,” Ph.D. dissertation, TU Darmstadt, 2011.

[11] A. Hadjakos, E. Aitenbichler, and M. Mühlhäuser, “Probabilistic model of pianists’ arm touch movements,” in *New Interfaces for Musical Expression 2009*, 2009, pp. 7–12.

[12] W. Goebel and C. Palmer, “Tactile feedback and timing accuracy in piano performance,” *Experimental Brain Research*, vol. 186, no. 3, pp. 471–479, 2008.

[13] S. Furuya and H. Kinoshita, “Expertise-dependent modulation of muscular and non-muscular torques in multi-joint arm movements during piano keystroke,” *Neuroscience*, vol. 156, pp. 390–402, 2008.

[14] A. Menache, *Understanding motion capture for computer animation and video games*. Morgan Kaufmann Pub, 2000.

[15] W. Goebel and C. Palmer, “Finger motion in piano performance: Touch and tempo,” in *International Symposium on Performance Science, ISPS 2009*. European Association of Conservatoires (AEC), 2009, pp. 65–70.

[16] C. Sforza, C. Macri, M. Turci, G. Grassi, and V. F. Ferrario, “Neuromuscular patterns of finger movements

- during piano playing. definition of an experimental protocol." *Ital J Anat Embryol.*, vol. 108, no. 4, pp. 211–222, 2003.
- [17] V. F. Ferrario, C. Macri, E. Biffi, P. Pollice, and C. Sforza, "Three-dimensional analysis of hand and finger movements during piano playing," *Medical Problems of Performing Artists*, vol. 22, no. 1, 2007.
- [18] J. Shotton, A. Fitzgibbon, M. Cook, T. Sharp, M. Finocchio, R. Moore, A. Kipman, and A. Blake, "Real-time human pose recognition in parts from single depth images," in *CVPR*, vol. 2, 2011, p. 7.
- [19] D. O. Gorodnichy and A. Yogeswaran, "Detection and tracking of pianist hands and fingers," in *Proc. of the The 3rd Canadian Conference on Computer and Robot Vision*, 2006.
- [20] G. Castellano, M. Mortillaro, A. Camurri, G. Volpe, and K. Scherer, "Automated analysis of body movement in emotionally expressive piano performances," *Music Perception*, pp. 103–119, 2008.
- [21] F. Klompaker, K. Nebe, and A. Fast, "dsensingni - a framework for advanced tangible interaction using a depth camera," in *Sixth International Conference on Tangible, Embedded and Embodied interaction (TEI)*, 2012.
- [22] "<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/kinect>."
- [23] H. Veeger, B. Yu, K. An, and R. Rozendal, "Parameters for modeling the upper extremity," *Journal of Biomechanics*, vol. 30, no. 6, pp. 647–652, 1997.